

Deliverable D3.3

Intermediate report on genetically modified poplar lines with effective performances on metal uptake and endophyte colonization

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.3 – report on genetically modified poplar lines with effective performances on metal uptake and endophyte colonization is the third deliverable of BIOSYSMO-WP3 - Development, optimization of biosystems. D3.3 is the result of Task 3.3 - Genetic engineering of poplar for improved soil phytoremediation. This document compiles data on relevant poplar genotypes with remediation capabilities, and the development poplar-endophyte colonization protocols.

Deliverable D3.3 describes, firstly, the methodologies to (1) perform metal tolerance assays and metal accumulation quantification in poplar (2) develop a protocol to inoculate poplar with endophytes, and (3) perform RNA-seq studies to identify candidate genes related to phytoremediation capabilities. Secondly, the report describes the results derived from T3.3 activities. The work developed in task T3.3 allowed the identification of two poplar tolerant genotypes for Zn and Cd excess. Moreover, RNA-seq analysis performed in T3.3 allowed the identification of new candidate genes for further genetic modifications to generate more tolerant and metal-accumulative poplar genotypes. Finally, because of Task 3.3 activities, we have developed an endophyte inoculation protocol for poplar that will allow us to test the impact of inoculating metal-tolerant poplar genotypes with relevant microbes isolated in the WP1 activities (D1.1) in terms of metal tolerance and metal transfer from soil to plant.

The final aim is to select and develop relevant plant-microbial combinations for phytoremediation for further activities in Task 4.2.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
WT	Wild type
OX	Overexpressing
KO	Knock-out
LD	Long Day
DEG	Differential Expressed Gene
TE	Trace Element
AM	Arbuscular Mycorrhiza
EM	Ectomycorrhiza

1 Introduction

Deliverable D3.3 describes the results of the work carried out by UPM and UBFC from WP3 Task 3.3, which focuses on the genetic engineering of poplar for improved soil phytoremediation. Our main objectives were A) to develop poplar genotypes (UPM) that are tolerant to and can accumulate Zn and Cd, which are the main pollutants of sites 1 and 10, as identified in WP1 activities. B) To characterize poplar-endophyte interaction (UBFC) of strains isolated from Task 1.2 and evaluate their performance under Zn and Cd excess, as it is reported in D1.1.

Poplar (*Populus* spp.) trees are well-suited for phytoremediation due to their fast growth rate and deep root systems. They can potentially absorb a significant amount of polluted water in water-rich areas but can still thrive in water-limited regions. Poplars are also considered a model tree species in forest genetics, genomics, and physiology due to their many advantages as a model system. These include rapid growth, prolific sexual reproduction, ease of cloning, small and sequenced genomes, genomic resources, facile transgenesis, and tight coupling between physiological traits and biomass productivity (Cronk, 2005).

Poplar plantations have been successfully used for heavy metal phytoremediation of polluted lands unsuitable for agriculture (Giachetti and Sebastiani, 2006). Meta-analysis of the reported investigation indicates that poplar can accumulate significant amounts of Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb, and Zn in all plant parts. However, the accumulation of Ni is only moderate, and Mn accumulation is limited, which is dependent on soil pH and exposure time (Tózsér et al, 2023). The mechanisms regulating plant - Zn and Cd interactions have been extensively studied in annual species with hyperaccumulating phenotypes (Unterbrunner et al, 2007; Takenaka et al, 2009; Zheleznova et al, 2017). However, these mechanisms are relatively unexplored in perennial species such as Poplar. The overexpression of poplar genes related to zinc accumulation from other species, such as HEAVY METAL TRANSPORTER (HMA4) and PHYTOCHELATIN (PCS1), nearly doubled the Zn accumulation in leaf tissues (Adams et al, 2011). This suggests that there may be a more significant pathway in perennials that should be investigated to engineer heavy metal hyperaccumulating poplars. It is also known that absorption and transport of both Zn and Cd in plants are strictly bound since Cd uses typical transporters implicated in Zn translocation such as HMA2 (Takahashi et al, 2012).

The phytohormone ethylene mediates heavy metal stress (Keunen et al, 2016; Thao et al, 2015). Recent work shows poplar treated with zinc excess triggers a hypoxic response and activates a battery of ethylene-related pathways. It is hypothesized that a component of the hypoxic response pathway might play a role in Zn tolerance and increase Zn accumulation capacity (Laura Dalle Carbonare et al, 2019).

UPM have explored the Zn and Cd tolerance and accumulation capacity caused by poplar ethylene response transcription factors associated with hypoxic response. We engineered overexpression and knock-out plants to perform functional studies under Zn and Cd excess. We developed Zn and Cd tolerance assays of trees under a controlled environment. Tree physiology and metal accumulation were monitored, identifying genotypes that show high tolerance and accumulation capacity under zinc excess. Comparative transcriptomic analyses are being conducted to unravel the molecular framework to improve poplar heavy metal hyperaccumulating phenotype.

However, the success of phytoremediation strategies depends on the capacity of plants to colonize stressed and degraded environments and indirectly on their ability to interact with soil microorganisms. Microorganisms are ubiquitous across environments and play critical roles within ecosystems and they

could create mutualistic associations with host organisms (Ciadamidaro et al., 2022; Chalot and Puschenreiter, 2021). Salicaceae trees, particularly poplar, have been widely studied for their ability to create diverse microbial associations, including rhizospheric and endophytic interactions with microorganisms (Beckers et al., 2017; Ciadamidaro et al., 2023). In our recent studies, we underlined the capacities of EM and AM inoculation on poplar cultivars “Skado”, growing at a multi-contaminated site, in enhancing biomass production (Ciadamidaro et al., 2017) and reducing TE translocation in leaves (Phanthavongsa et al., 2017). In the past few years, special attention has been given to the use of inoculation of plants with microbial consortia, responsible for improving plant TE uptake and accumulation in phytoextraction techniques or limiting TE translocation from roots to shoots in phytostabilisation processes.

As a consequence of Task 3.3 activities, Zn and Cd tolerant and accumulative engineered (knock out plants by CRISPR-Cas9 and overexpressing) poplar lines have been described. Moreover, new genes have been selected for further genetic modifications for new Zn and Cd tolerant and accumulative poplar genotypes (UPM).

As a result of WP1 and WP3 activities, relevant microbes have been isolated (D1.2) and characterized (D3.1) from the rhizosphere of woody species collected at various polluted sites (UBFC). Some of these microbes have shown some relevant PGP capacities, especially with willow as a model plant.

As a major innovation, the best-performing poplar genotypes will be biodynamized by selected microbial consortia and tested for their capacities to increase the export of metals to the aboveground tissues and to improve metal sequestration within the rhizosphere. Overall, this will lead to a bioaugmented, genetically engineered-based phytoremediation strategy that has never been applied to poplar.

Selected poplar genotypes and microbial consortia will be used for the soil phytoremediation strategy that is part of Task 4.2 activities.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Plant material and growth conditions

Populus tremula × *alba* INRA clone 717 1B4 was cultured in vitro in Murashige and Skoog (MS-Duchefa). Growth conditions of photoperiod were long-day (LD) (16 h of light and 8 h of dark) and 22°C for temperature. Four-weeks-old in vitro poplar plantlets were transferred to perlite pots for metal tolerance testing. Perlite was previously washed with water to remove any excess of dust. Plants were growing in LD photoperiodic conditions and 22°C for six to eight weeks and supplemented with 0.5 g/L of Peters Professional 20-20-20 (Comercial Química Massó, Barcelona, Spain) once every two weeks before the addition of the heavy metal solution.

2.2 Production of microbial inocula and poplar inoculation protocol

The fungal inocula were prepared in 500 ml glass jars in which 250 ml of perlite were mixed with 250 ml of MEA medium. After sterilization, 6 fungal agar implants (0.8 cm diameter) were mixed with the perlite. The jars were incubated in the dark for three to four weeks at 24°C and were shaken every seven days to ensure homogeneous development of the inoculum. The inoculated perlite was mixed (1:10) with the TE-contaminated soil that was previously sterilized by three successive autoclaving steps (120 °C for 20 min, 2-day intervals between each step). Two hundred twenty-five grams of sterilized soil were added in 300-ml pots together with 25 g of fungal inoculum.

In vitro poplar plantlets were produced as described above and were planted in each pot (n=10 per fungal species). Plants were placed in a growth chamber for 12 weeks (24°C, 16 h light per day, 90% moisture).

The plants will be harvested and successively washed with three baths (tap water and distilled water). Several plant parameters were measured, such as plant biomass, leaf area, or plant TE concentrations. To determine the fresh biomass, the roots were weighed separately from the aerial part of the plant. The leaves were scanned, and their area was determined using the ImageJ software. Then, the leaves and the stems were placed in a forced-air oven at 70°C for at least 48 hours and grounded using a stainless-steel mill. Samples were then mineralized in HNO₃ (68%) and H₂O₂ (30%), filtered and analysed by ICP-AES.

2.3 Metal tolerance assays

ZnCl₂ anhydrous 99,9% (Fisher) and CdCl₂ anhydrous 99,9% (Fisher) salts were used for metal tolerance testing. To determine the most effective concentration for the assays, wild type poplar plants were exposed to 150 µM, 300 µM and 600 µM of ZnCl₂, or 50 µM, 100 µM, 200 µM and 300 µM of CdCl₂. This range of concentrations was chosen based on previous similar studies from bibliography (Di Baccio et al, 2003; He et al, 2013; Di Baccio et al, 2014).

In the study, metal tolerance assays were conducted by treating the plants with 300 mL of 600 µM ZnCl₂ aqueous solution for eight weeks and 300 mL of 300 µM of CdCl₂ aqueous solution for five weeks in the case of CdCl₂. These concentrations were selected due to best performance in the previous screening to determine the most effective concentration for the assays. Control plants, on the other

hand, were only treated with water. It's worth noting that the experiment ended once the wild-type poplar plants died due to metal toxicity.

- **Monitoring plant physiology (UPM)**

Plants physiology parameters of stomata conductance and photosystem II activity were measured using a CIRAS-3 Portable Photosynthesis System (PP Systems). After the assay, the fresh weight of roots and stem was measured using a weighing machine.

- **Determination of metals concentration (UBFC)**

Metal concentrations in plant tissues were measured from plant dried material after milling and mineralization. Total metal concentrations of leaves and roots were determined in wet-digested samples in HNO₃ and H₂O₂. After filtration to 1 µm was performed, metal concentrations were determined using the ICP-AES analysis (Radial ICAP 6500 Model, Thermo Fischer Scientific, Courtaboeuf, France) (Assad et al., 2017). All samples were analysed in triplicate with the certified reference materials oriental Basma tobacco leaves (INCT-OBTL-5, LGC Promochem, Molsheim, France).

2.4 RNA-seq studies

- **Sample preparation**

For RNA-seq analysis, the plants were treated with a solution containing 600 µM ZnCl₂ once a week for four weeks before sample collection. The samples were collected by cutting the leaves and immediately freezing them in liquid nitrogen. RNA extraction was performed in frozen ground leaf material by adding cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) extraction buffer with 2% β-mercaptoethanol at 65°C for 5 min, followed by washing with chloroform twice. RNA was precipitated by adding 7.5 M LiCl₂: 50 mM EDTA and incubated overnight at 4°C. RNA was collected by centrifuging at 10,000 RPM for 20 min at 4°C and then purified according to the manufacturer's instructions of NZY RNA purification kit (NZYTech, Lisbon, Portugal) and eluted in water. The RNA was then sent to Macrogen Inc. (Seoul, Republic of Korea) for Illumina TruSeq stranded mRNA library generation and Illumina 150bp PE sequencing.

- **Quality control**

The raw reads of FASTQ files obtained after sequencing undergo quality assessment and filtering using the FastQC package. This step allows us to identify adapter content and low-quality reads. These issues are first fixed by trimming the Illumina adapter sequences using the trimmomatic package [<https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu170>]. Second, the reads are also filtered based on their quality score using the leading, trailing, and sliding window parameters with standard values defined by the trimmomatic tool.

- **Alignment (UPM)**

To map our reads against a reference genome, the STAR (Spliced Transcripts Alignment to a Reference) package [10.1093/bioinformatics/bts635] is used. The genome FASTA and GTF files of our *Populus alba* reference genome can be acquired from the phytozome website (<https://phytozome-next.jgi.doe.gov>). *Populus alba* genome and the trimmed reads from the quality control step are used as input to the STAR aligner to map the reads to the genome. The alignment results are saved in BAM. As a final step, the generated BAM files are used as input to the featureCounts package (Liao et al, 2014) that counts mapped reads for each gene.

- **Gene expression analysis (UPM)**

To discover quantitative changes in expression levels, differential gene expression analysis is performed using the Bioconductor EdgeR package (Robinson et al, 2010). The obtained counts of the mapped reads per gene are used as an input to EdgeR. For further analysis and data mining, differentially expressed genes are filtered based on the adjusted p-value, where all the genes with an adjusted p-value higher than 0.01 are discarded.

3 Results

3.1 Searching for metal-tolerant poplar genotypes by metal tolerance assays

3.1.1 ZnCl₂ tolerance assays in poplar

To find the most effective stress-inducing treatment of ZnCl₂, we exposed WT poplars to different concentrations of ZnCl₂ (150 μM, 300 μM, and 600 μM) once a week for 8 weeks (Fig. 1). We observed that higher concentrations of ZnCl₂ led to less growth and development of plants, and eventually to their death. While 150 μM of ZnCl₂ did not cause any significant visual changes in the plant, 300 μM of ZnCl₂ resulted in a substantial loss of vigour, and 600 μM of ZnCl₂ caused the plant to die after the treatments. Based on these observations, we concluded that 600 μM of ZnCl₂ was the most effective and optimal concentration for performing tolerance assays in poplar. This concentration will allow us to determine if a different poplar genotype can survive this concentration, unlike the WT poplar, within a reasonable experimental time.

Figure 1. Screening of WT poplars to find the most effective concentration of ZnCl₂ for metal tolerance assays. The picture shows plants exposed to 150 μM, 300 μM and 600 μM of ZnCl₂ once a week after eight weeks. N=6 for each genotype and treatment.

After choosing the most efficient concentration for metal tolerance experiments, we tested the effects of overexpressing and knocking out, by CRISPR-Cas9, GENE1 in plants. GENE1 is a transcription factor that responds to ethylene, a hormone induced by heavy metal stress. We believe that poplar

plants with engineered GENE1 genotypes have the potential to tolerate and accumulate metals successfully.

WT poplar was used as a genotype control in the metal tolerance experiment. Two independent knock-out (CRISPR-Cas9) lines and three independent overexpressing lines were also used. The treatment group of plants was given a weekly dose of 300 mL of 600 μM ZnCl_2 aqueous solution, while the control group was only given water. As shown in Figure 2A-B, after eight weeks of treatment, the WT plant and GENE1 knock-out lines #12 and #16 were completely dead, whereas GENE1 overexpressing lines #3, #6, and #11 remained alive, as evidenced by comparison with the control conditions.

Figure 2. ZnCl_2 tolerance assay of GENE1 poplar genotypes. Images of comparison between the different poplar genotypes after eight weeks of control conditions (A) and plants after eight weeks of weekly treatment with 300 mL of 600 μM ZnCl_2 (B). Stem fresh weight (C) and roots fresh weight (D) poplar genotypes after eight weeks in control conditions and after eight weeks of weekly treatment with 300 mL of 600 μM ZnCl_2 , measured in grams. Stomata conductance measured in $\text{mmol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (E) and photosystem II activity (F) of the different poplar genotypes after eight weeks in control conditions and after eight weeks of weekly treatment with 300 mL of 600 μM ZnCl_2 . N=6 for each genotype and treatment.

We went beyond visual phenotyping and decided to monitor the physiology of plants (Fig. 2 C-E). We measured the fresh weight of the stem (Fig. 2C) and roots (Fig. 2D) to indicate the plants' vigour. We found that the GENE1 OX lines could maintain a higher fresh weight of both organs under treatment conditions than the GENE1 KO lines and WT poplar. However, we observed fresh weight loss for all genotypes in treatment conditions due to stress caused by ZnCl_2 . We also measured stomata conductance (Fig. 2E), which shows the level of stomata activity. Under treatment conditions, neither WT nor GENE1 KO lines showed any stomata activity, as the plants were dead when we phenotyped them. In contrast, GENE1 OX lines showed stomata activity, indicating they were alive. Again, stomata activity was lost for all overexpressing genotypes under treatment conditions due to stress caused by ZnCl_2 . We also evaluated the activity of photosystem II (Fig. 2F). Both WT and GENE1 KO lines showed no photosynthetic activity under treatment conditions, while GENE1 OX lines showed similar photosystem II activity in both treatment and control conditions.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that GENE1 OX is a poplar genotype tolerant to Zn^{2+} . To further study this genotype, we measure metal concentration in the tissues of the tolerant plants. This was done to confirm whether they can accumulate the metal in their tissues. Metal concentrations were determined using ICP-AES analysis. As shown in Figure 3, the GENE1 OX lines significantly duplicated Zn^{2+} content in their leaves (Figure 3A) compared to the WT poplar. However, there were no significant differences in Zn^{2+} content in the roots between the WT and OX lines (Figure 3B).

Figure 3. Zn^{2+} concentration in poplar tissues. Zn^{2+} content in leaves in control and treatment conditions and Zn^{2+} concentration in roots in control and treatment conditions for both WT and GENE1 OX plants. Concentration is measured in mg/kg. N=6 for each genotype and treatment. N=6 for each genotype and treatment.

We have found that GENE1 OX can tolerate an excess of Zn^{2+} and specifically accumulate it in leaves, making it a potentially helpful plant for phytoextraction.

We have also tested another ethylene response factor that could tolerate and accumulate metals. For the first screening approach, we tested one knock-out (CRISPR-Cas9) line of GENE2 (GENE2 KO #6) and treated WT and GENE2 KO plants with different $ZnCl_2$ concentrations. Figure 4 shows the results of this experiment. As we can see in the figure, the WT plant under 300 µM of $ZnCl_2$ treatment barely shows any stress symptoms, whereas the GENE2 KO plant under 300 µM of $ZnCl_2$ treatment shows a complete loss of leaves along the stem and almost death. In contrast, the GENE2 KO plant under 150 µM of $ZnCl_2$ treatment shows an intermediate phenotype. This result indicates that the GENE2 KO genotype is sensitive to Zn^{2+} stress. We hypothesize that GENE2 overexpressing genotypes could potentially be tolerant and accumulator genotypes in the same way as GENE1 is. We are currently running an experiment with a similar design to the one carried out with GENE1 genotypes (Figure 2), and the final results of these experiments will be available in the coming weeks.

Figure 4. ZnCl₂ tolerance assay of GENE2 KO poplar genotype. Image shows a visual phenotype comparison between WT poplar treated weekly with 300 μM ZnCl₂, GENE2 KO #6 treated with 150 μM ZnCl₂ and GENE2 KO #6 treated with 300 μM ZnCl₂. Treatments were performed weekly for eight weeks. N=6 for each genotype and treatment.

3.1.2 CdCl₂ tolerance assays in poplar

To determine the most effective concentration of CdCl₂, WT poplars were exposed to different concentrations of CdCl₂ (50 μM, 100 μM, 200 μM, and 300 μM) once a week for four weeks (as shown in Figure 5). Every concentration of CdCl₂ caused stress on the plants, with higher concentrations leading to less growth and development, and eventual death. Although 50 μM, 100 μM, and 200 μM of CdCl₂ did not cause significant visual changes in the plants beyond changes in the leaf colour due to stress, 300 μM of CdCl₂ resulted in a significant loss of plant vigour, and the lower parts of the plant died after treatment. In conclusion, 300 μM of CdCl₂ was the most effective and optimal concentration to carry out the following tolerance assays in poplar. This concentration will help us determine whether a different poplar genotype can survive this concentration, unlike the WT one, in a reasonable experimental time.

Figure 5. Screening of WT poplars to find the most effective concentration of CdCl₂ for metal tolerance assays. The picture shows plants exposed to 50 μM, 100 μM, 200 μM and 300 μM of CdCl₂ once a week after eight weeks.

Once we had the most effective concentration for the Cd tolerance experiments, we proceeded to test the GENE1 genotypes. As in the Zn tolerance assay, WT poplar was used as a genotype control. Two independent knock-out lines and three independent overexpressing lines were also used. The treatment group of plants was given a weekly dose of 300 mL of 300 μM CdCl₂ aqueous solution, while the control group was only given water. The experiment is currently ongoing, and Figure 6 shows the present state of the plants after five weeks of treatment. As it is shown, no genotype is dead at this point. However, as in Zn tolerance assay, we can appreciate that WT poplar and GENE1 knock-out lines #12 and #16 (Figure 6B) show significant signs of stress, such as death and loss of leaves from bottom to top part of the plant and a decrease of general vigour, as evidence by contrast with control conditions (Figure 6A). In contrast, GENE1 overexpressing lines #3, #6, and #11, except the loss of general vigour because of Cd toxicity, bottom leaves remain alive and general appearance of plants is clearly healthier than WT in treatment conditions, though some redness of top leaves.

Figure 6. CdCl₂ tolerance assay of GENE1 poplar genotypes. Images of comparison between the different poplar genotypes after five weeks of control conditions (A) and plants after five weeks of weekly treatment with 300 mL of 300 μM CdCl₂ (B).

We will report the final result of the experiment once it is over and WT plants are completely dead. We will monitor and measure the physiological parameters to have a phenotype profile of the GENE1 genotypes in response to Cd. Even though the experiment has not concluded yet, we are completely sure that it will be successful due to the evolution of the plants in the different conditions.

3.2 Finding new target genes for poplar genetic engineering by RNA-seq analysis

To further analyse and exploit our promising phytoextractor and hyperaccumulator GENE1 poplar genotype, we performed an RNA-seq experiment. With this approach, we aim to better understand the molecular mechanism implicated in the capacity of GENE1 poplar genotype to tolerate an excess of Zn and accumulate this element. Also, we aim to use RNA-seq analysis to find new and better genetic targets for further genetic modifications that can optimize tolerance and accumulation of metals in poplar.

The experimental design for the RNA-seq studies was similar to the one used for ZnCl₂ tolerance assays (Figure 2). We used WT, GENE1 OX #11 and GENE1 KO #16 lines based on their performance in the

tolerance assay. We used 6 plants of every genotype for each treatment (control and 600 μM of ZnCl_2), so a total of 36 plants were used.

After four weeks of weekly treatment to the treatment plant group with 300 mL of 600 μM ZnCl_2 , plants developed visual metal stress phenotype, so we collected the leaf samples. We collected 3 replicates of every treatment as the best way to have robust RNA-seq results. Each replicate consists of one leaf from two different plants treated in the same conditions. We thus collected 3 different samples of WT poplar both in control and 600 μM ZnCl_2 conditions, GENE1 OX #11 poplar both in control and 600 μM ZnCl_2 conditions and GENE1 KO #16 poplar both in control and 600 μM ZnCl_2 conditions.

RNA extraction was performed as described in the methods. RNA samples were sent to Macrogen Inc. (Seoul, Republic of Korea) for Illumina TruSeq stranded mRNA library generation and Illumina 150bp PE sequencing.

Sequencing, quality control and alignment were performed as described in methods. In Table 1 we show the first raw data from aligning the sequences to *Populus alba* reference genome.

Table 1. Mapped data stats from RNA-seq analysis. Sample column refers to individual type of genotype, treatment and number of replicates used for sequencing. Processed reads refer to the number of cleaned reads after trimming. Mapped reads column refers to the total number of reads mapped to reference genome. The unmapped reads column refers to the total number of reads that failed to align to the reference genome.

Sample	Processed reads	Mapped reads	Unmapped reads
WT Control 1	52,652,846	48,657,554 (92.41%)	3,995,292 (7.59%)
WT Control 2	58,324,990	53,837,561 (92.31%)	4,487,429 (7.69%)
WT Control 3	58,305,612	53,347,637 (91.5%)	4,957,975 (8.5%)
WT ZnCl_2 1	58,316,590	53,677,704 (92.05%)	4,638,886 (7.95%)
WT ZnCl_2 2	58,046,548	53,098,067 (91.47%)	4,948,481 (8.53%)
WT ZnCl_2 3	58,169,476	53,345,138 (91.71%)	4,824,338 (8.29%)
GENE1 OX #11 Control 1	53,963,256	49,855,404 (92.39%)	4,107,852 (7.61%)
GENE1 OX #11 Control 2	55,708,952	51,378,793 (92.23%)	4,330,159 (7.77%)
GENE1 OX #11 Control 3	58,468,090	53,608,104 (91.69%)	4,859,986 (8.31%)
GENE1 OX #11 ZnCl_2 1	58,220,190	52,731,252 (90.57%)	5,488,938 (9.43%)
GENE1 OX #11 ZnCl_2 2	58,362,430	53,677,969 (91.97%)	4,684,461 (8.03%)
GENE1 OX #11 ZnCl_2 3	57,927,304	52,873,377 (91.28%)	5,053,927 (8.72%)
GENE1 KO #16 Control 1	58,336,792	53,471,701 (91.66%)	4,865,091 (8.34%)
GENE1 KO #16 Control 2	58,289,670	53,104,760 (91.1%)	5,184,910 (8.9%)
GENE1 KO #16 Control 3	57,911,142	52,494,181 (90.65%)	5,416,961 (9.35%)
GENE1 KO #16 ZnCl_2 1	58,467,182	53,503,779 (91.51%)	4,963,403 (8.49%)
GENE1 KO #16 ZnCl_2 2	58,232,426	53,392,736 (91.69%)	4,839,690 (8.31%)
GENE1 KO #16 ZnCl_2 3	58,283,744	53,416,096 (91.65%)	4,867,648 (8.35%)

With all this data, we performed the gene expression analysis using EdgeR as described in methods to obtain candidate genes for further genetic modifications in poplar. The first step was to obtain lists of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) between the control and Zn conditions of every genotype. Thereby, we generated 3 different DEGs lists:

- WT Control / WT ZnCl₂
- GENE1 OX Control / GENE1 OX ZnCl₂
- GENE1 KO Control / GENE1 KO ZnCl₂

Once we had these lists of DEGs, we generated a Venn Diagram (Figure 7) to see common and non-common genes between these lists.

Figure 7. Venn Diagram of RNA-seq results. The diagram shows the intersections between the DEGs lists. On one hand common DEGs between genotypes and on the other hand unique DEGs of every genotype.

This result, together with further analysis of the function of the genes will give us a considerable amount of biological information to understand tolerance and accumulative behaviour of GENE1 OX poplar genotype and will lead us to select candidate genes for the upcoming genetic modifications.

We will perform functional bioinformatic studies of the obtained genes from these lists to select candidates implicated in metal-related functions, such as metal metabolism, transport and translocation, metal stress response and signalling, and metal tolerance and accumulation.

Also, in the coming months, we will perform another RNA-seq experiment with GENE1 genotypes exposed to CdCl₂ to improve the understanding of this genotype in response to metals and to complement and refine the transcriptomic analysis.

3.3 Selection of poplar microbe assemblages

As a starting point, UBFC has grown the poplar genotype 717-1-B4 and inoculated it with a panel of fungal strains isolated from T1.2. The inoculation process is described in section 2.2 above. The experiment is still ongoing and will facilitate the selection and development of appropriate microbe assemblages for further activities.

4 Conclusions and future activities

- As a result of Task 3.3 activities, one Zn and Cd tolerant and accumulative poplar line (GENE1 OX) has been selected. This line will be further used for Task 4.2 activities to test the future developed microbial consortium. Other already generated promising lines, such as GENE2 OX, will be tested for tolerance and accumulation of Zn and Cd, and they will be further used for Task 4.2 activities too (UPM).
- As a result of Task 3.3 activities, we have obtained a list of candidate genes through an RNA-seq experiment. Thus, in the coming months we will perform genetic modifications of selected candidate genes to increase the number of Zn and Cd tolerant and accumulative poplar lines. These lines will probably be further used for Task 4.2 activities (UPM).
- As a result of WP1 activities, relevant microbes have been isolated (D1.1) and characterized (D3.1) from various sites. Some of these microbes have shown relevant PGP capacities, especially with willow as a model plant. In Task 3.1, ongoing activities allow to confront the relevant poplar genotypes described in this deliverable, with these most relevant microbes. The objective is to evaluate the impact of the inoculation of the most metal tolerant poplar genotypes with the most metal tolerant microbes, in terms of metal bioavailability and transfer from soil to plant. The final aim is to select and develop an appropriate microbial consortium for further activities in Task 4.2 (UBFC).

5 References

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